

Polar decomposition of Mueller matrices by quaternion decomposition and quaternion polar forms

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Abstract

A nondepolarizing Mueller matrix can be written as a commutative product of a complex matrix \mathbf{Z} and its complex conjugate ($\mathbf{M}=\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^*=\mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z}$). Polar decomposition of the Mueller matrix can be easily done by first subjecting the \mathbf{Z} matrix to a polar decomposition. Using the property that the \mathbf{Z} matrix is isomorphic to the associated quaternion it is also possible to exploit the quaternion polar forms to calculate matrix inverses and square roots.

Mueller matrix of a nondepolarizing optical medium can be written as a commutative product of left- and right-isoclinic transformations \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* in 4D complex space

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z} \quad (1)$$

where $*$ denotes complex conjugation and \mathbf{Z} is defined as

$$\mathbf{Z} = \tau\mathbf{1} + i\alpha\mathbf{I} + i\beta\mathbf{J} + i\gamma\mathbf{K} \quad (2)$$

τ, α, β and γ are complex anisotropy parameters that can be defined in terms of basic spectroscopic parameters and they can be calculated from the Mueller matrix as described in the Appendix, $\mathbf{1}$ is the identity, \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{K} can be read as quaternion imaginary units for the quaternion representation of \mathbf{Z} , or they can be replaced by 4×4 matrices for the matrix representation of \mathbf{Z} . Explicit form is given in the Appendix.

Polar decomposition of the \mathbf{Z} matrix is very easy and immediately entails the polar decomposition of the Mueller matrix:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}_U\mathbf{Z}_H \rightarrow (\mathbf{Z}_U\mathbf{Z}_H)(\mathbf{Z}_U\mathbf{Z}_H)^* = (\mathbf{Z}_U\mathbf{Z}_U^*)(\mathbf{Z}_H\mathbf{Z}_H^*) = \mathbf{M}_U\mathbf{M}_H \quad (3)$$

As a first step consider the product $\mathbf{Z}^\dagger\mathbf{Z}$, where \dagger denotes the Hermitian conjugate. It can be easily verified that $\mathbf{Z}^\dagger\mathbf{Z}$ is a real quaternion with coefficients being the first row of the Mueller matrix

$$\mathbf{Z}^\dagger\mathbf{Z} = m_{00}\mathbf{1} + im_{01}\mathbf{I} + im_{02}\mathbf{J} + im_{03}\mathbf{K} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, $\mathbf{Z}_H = \sqrt{\mathbf{Z}^\dagger\mathbf{Z}}$ and $\mathbf{Z}_U = \mathbf{Z}\sqrt{\mathbf{Z}^\dagger\mathbf{Z}}^{-1}$. Similarly, decomposition in the form $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}_H\mathbf{Z}_U$ is also possible via $\sqrt{\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^\dagger}$. In this case, $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^\dagger$ is given by the first column of the Mueller matrix.

Inverse of \mathbf{Z} is simply

$$\mathbf{Z}^{-1} = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{Z}}}{|\mathbf{Z}|^2} \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{Z}} = \tau\mathbf{1} - i\alpha\mathbf{I} - i\beta\mathbf{J} - i\gamma\mathbf{K}$ and $|\mathbf{Z}|^2 = \mathbf{Z}\bar{\mathbf{Z}} = \tau^2 - \alpha^2 - \beta^2 - \gamma^2$, or $|\mathbf{Z}|^2 = \det(\mathbf{Z})^{1/2}$.

Square root of \mathbf{Z} is also straightforward with the quaternion polar form:

$$\mathbf{Z} = r(\cos(\theta)\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{n} \cdot \sigma \sin(\theta)) \quad (6)$$

where $r = |\mathbf{Z}|$, $\theta = \arctan \sqrt{-(\alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \gamma^2)/\tau^2}$,

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \gamma^2}}, \quad \sigma = (\mathbf{I}, \mathbf{J}, \mathbf{K}) \quad (7)$$

Then,

$$\sqrt{\mathbf{Z}} = \sqrt{r}(\cos(\theta/2)\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{n} \cdot \sigma \sin(\theta/2)) \quad (8)$$

Appendix

\mathbf{Z} matrix is defined in an exponential form in terms of the spectroscopic parameters, isotropic phase retardation (η), isotropic amplitude absorption (κ), circular dichroism (CD), circular birefringence (CB), horizontal and 45° linear dichroism (LD and LD'), horizontal and 45° linear birefringence (LB and LB'):

$$\mathbf{Z} = e^{\mathbf{z}} \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{z} is

$$\mathbf{z} = -\frac{i}{2}(\chi\mathbf{1} + iL\mathbf{I} + iL'\mathbf{J} - iC\mathbf{K}) \quad (10)$$

\mathbf{I} , \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{K} are the Hamilton's imaginary units, $\chi = \eta - i\kappa$, $L = LB - iLD$, $L' = LB' - iLD'$, $C = CB - iCD$. In this expression \mathbf{z} is a quaternion with complex variables, but it can also be read as a matrix in terms of the matrix representations of \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{K} :

$$\mathbf{1} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{I} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{J} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{K} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Series expansion of $e^{\mathbf{z}}$ gives

$$\mathbf{Z} = \tau\mathbf{1} + i\alpha\mathbf{I} + i\beta\mathbf{J} + i\gamma\mathbf{K} \quad (12)$$

Explicitly,

$$\tau = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \alpha = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$\beta = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL'}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \gamma = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iC}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (14)$$

where $T = \sqrt{L^2 + L'^2 + C^2}$.

In matrix form

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \beta & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Reverse procedure is also possible. We can derive L , L' and C from τ , α , β and γ by first calculating $T/2$

$$T/2 = \arctan \sqrt{-(\alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \gamma^2)/\tau^2} \quad (16)$$

then

$$L = \frac{i\alpha T}{\tau} \cot(T/2), \quad L' = \frac{i\beta T}{\tau} \cot(T/2), \quad C = -\frac{i\gamma T}{\tau} \cot(T/2), \quad (17)$$

If we have a nondepolarizing Mueller matrix we can find values of τ , α , β and γ by transforming \mathbf{M} into a Hermitian matrix \mathbf{H} :

$$\mathbf{H} = \sum_{i,j=0}^3 m_{ij} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i \otimes \boldsymbol{\sigma}_j^*), \quad (18)$$

where m_{ij} are the elements of \mathbf{M} and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$ are the Pauli matrices with the 2×2 identity matrix $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0$ in the following order:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

If the Mueller matrix of the system is non-depolarizing, the associated \mathbf{H} matrix will be of rank 1, and τ , α , β and γ can be directly read from the elements of any non-zero column of \mathbf{H} . Then, we can apply Eqs. 16 and 17 to find L , L' and C . The parameters τ , α , β and γ extracted from the Mueller matrix may differ by the same constant factor from the ones that given in Eqs. 13 and 14 but this does not affect the results of Eqs. 16 and 17.

References

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